

Research

China-Afghanistan Bilateral International Relations

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Abstract: China is one of the key power that has its involvement in Afghanistan due to two countries adjoin. This paper aims to analyse of the strategic, political and economic interests of China and explores the challenges it faces in achieving these objectives. Terrorism and drug trafficking are the two threats that put China's interests at stake in the region. China has minimal support and has limited and difficult choices to enhance its influence, secure its interest, and to cope with existing challenges. As a new powerful actor in world international politics, interested in stable states near its borders. Thus, the recent US withdrawal from Afghanistan created new opportunities for China, where China identifies four main goals in its foreign policy cooperation with Afghanistan as follows: regional peace; developing both countries' economies; strengthening governance in Afghanistan and fourth, acquiring international support. These approaches are maintained by Chinese investments into Afghanistan's economy as it remains one of the largest investors in Afghanistan.

Keywords: China, Afghanistan, China's interests, Sino-Afghanistan Relationship

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Brief history of Sino-Afghanistan Relationship

The Sino-Afghan relationship started back in the 7th century when Buddha statues in Bamyian province attracted the first Chinese monks. Because China used to be the Asian trade hub, Afghanistan served as a transit route between the two countries. The Silk Road ran through Bamyian province for approximately 76 kilometers therefore Afghanistan has been linking Asia and Europe. The two countries have been sharing mutual respect and understanding as they have no political or ideological differences¹ and have never faced any differences in the past². Two neighboring countries established their bilateral relationship in 1950.

However, the diplomatic ties between the two neighbors were established in 1957, when Abdul Samand, Afghanistan's first ambassador, was posted to China on January 20, 1955. In 1957, Chinese Prime Minister Zhu Enlai

¹ Hsiung C.J. (2009). The Age of Geo-Economics, China's Global Role, and Prospects of Cross-Strait Integration. *Journal of Chinese Political Science*, 14(2):113-133.

² Ng T.P. (2010). China's Role in Shaping the future of Afghanistan. *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*.

traveled to Afghanistan during the Cold War. Earlier in the same year, President Daud Khan traveled to Beijing where he met with China's top officials to discuss fostering mutual understanding and positive trade relations³. These trips improved Afghanistan's and the People's Republic of China's bilateral ties. In August 1960, the Sino-Afghan Treaty of Friendship and Non-Aggression was signed. After that, in 1963, China and Afghanistan officially delineated their border through the Peking Treaty, resolving all outstanding disputes about their 76-kilometer-long border. Afghanistan remains significant for China due to its location providing the most straightforward transportation route for the development of energy and mineral resources both within Afghanistan and in its neighboring Central Asian and Caucasian regions.

With the signing of the "Treaty of Economic and Technical Cooperation" in 1964, relations between China and Afghanistan became official. China has emerged as one of the primary exporters to Afghanistan over the past ten years as trade between the two nations has gradually increased in recent years. China has become one of the top exporters to Afghanistan over the past ten years as trade between the two countries has gradually grown. China Metallurgical Corporation (MCC) and Jiangxi Copper Corporation (JCCL) received a tender to develop the world's second-largest copper deposit (Aynak in Logar Province, 35 kilometers southeast of Kabul) and invested US\$3.5 billion in the Afghan economy. The estimated value of these copper resources ranges from \$1 to \$3 trillion. Afghanistan was granted membership status in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), a regional alliance and organization that seeks to promote peace, stability, and cooperation in economy, politics, defense, and security, and of which China is a significant part, at the beginning of 2016⁴. In 2018, the amount of their bilateral trade reached \$544 million⁵.

Sino-Afghan Strategic Relationship

China is one in all the key power that has its involvement in Afghanistan because of two countries adjoin. Now after the withdrawal folks forces from Afghanistan, a replacement great game is within the offing within the region and China also has its own interest. Modern Chinese diplomacy has gone through several stages of development over the past three decades. Initially, Afghanistan didn't gain central importance within the policy of China but now with the changing political dynamics within the region, it had attained the special attention of China. The geostrategic position of Afghanistan is form of important for China because it'll be the a part of the OBOR project in near future. It's mentioned within the IMF report (2015) that China has decided to require a grip \$100 million in Afghanistan out of \$890 billion-grand OBOR project which is further comprised of over 900 projects- because it's an inevitable part of China's neighborhood diplomacy⁶.

Geography plays a vital role on the chessboard of worldwide in the international politics. This idea has already been observed as playing its role just in case of China that's traditionally viewed as a continental power due to its extended geography. China is one among the powerful members of BRIC (Brazil, Russia, India, and China) these emerging economies have brought an entire shift within the paradigm of worldwide politics. Their power and strength lie not

³ Van Derven, *Warfare in Chinese history* (Vol. 47). Brill, 2000.

⁴ Stanzel Angela. (2016). *China's investment in influence : the future of 16+1 cooperation*. European Council On foreign Relations.

⁵ Zia H. (2019). *A surge in China-Afghsnistan Trade*. China Daily.

⁶ Mudabber Zabihullah. (2016). "Where Does Afghanistan Fit in China's Belt and Road? Cssfom: <http://www.cssforum.com.pk/general/news-articles/foreign-newspaper/109173-where-does-afganistan-fit-china-s-belt-road.html>.

only in their economic process but also in their population and land -as BRICS territories cover 40% of the world population in the BRICS territories⁷. The Chinese approach is based on the use of labor in their policies, which is supported in the long term by the state.

"Silk Road" and "One Belt One Road" (OBOR) shows that China's prime intent is to become a rising economic power within the world. These megaprojects are supported a two-fold strategy: one is internal reforms to regain the economic momentum and therefore the other is to reinforce its international position while satisfying its national security needs.

Afghanistan is one among the potential and feasible countries where Chinese economic approaches ambitions may be, partially, satiated. Situated within the Southwest of China, it's a landlocked country. Both states have a typical border of 76 km within the northeastern mountain area. From a historical viewpoint, both states had been connected through old trade route which linked Rome to China through Afghanistan around 2000 years ago. Both Afghanistan and China had recognized one another as independent states during 1950 and 1955 respectively. During the following years, the Sino-Afghan relations went through several phases with the arrival of successive governments and introduction of rational policies. The standard passive approach of Chinese policy towards Afghanistan has become a vigorous approach since 2001. The relations between both the states are supported by a common interest. The campaign for peace and work for prosperity are the most dominant aspects of this partnership. The mines, trade, and transit are the main areas need private investments in Afghanistan.

China's approaches toward Afghanistan are based on four general factors, which are: security and stability, economy and governance suitable to Afghanistan enhancing international cooperation.

Thus, the essence of China's policy towards Afghanistan is based on the principles of Afghan-led and Afghan-owned initiatives and processes to maintain the country's independence, its territorial integrity, and accept the path chosen by the people of the country for her progress. Beijing has always advocated the peaceful resolution of conflicts and the maintenance of peace in the region. This is often the reason why he enforces a strict anti-terrorism policy in Xinjiang province. In addition, he was also a great advocate for a non-military solution and lasting peace in Afghanistan. So, in a nutshell, 2 main interests determine China's policy in Afghanistan, security, and economy.

Some experts are of the opinion that there are four priorities in Afghan politics: political reconciliation, the fight against terrorism and drugs, good governance, and economic development. Afghanistan is facing internal and external pressures and is fighting simultaneously on different fronts. On the one hand, the country faces challenges such as the activities of anti-state actors, militancy and a weak law and order situation after 2014, and a surge in militant attacks during 2017. However, Kabul politics and the Afghan National Security Forces (ANSF) have tried many times to bring the deteriorating situation under control. While, on the contrary, the international community is forcing him to demand responsibility for his national security at the expense of his own budget, and not count on international assistance. It is quite difficult for a war-torn country to demand control of social problems such as human and drug trafficking, national security, and domestic economic development in the absence of international financial assistance and personal income. In this pathetic state, regional economic integration favors Afghanistan in attracting foreign investment and assets to benefit from its vast resources, mineral deposits, and transport infrastructure.

To develop a long-term partnership, China and Afghanistan need each other's support and assistance to meet their needs and achieve their goals. The only factor hindering the event in Afghanistan, in the meantime, hindering China's adequate investment, is the weak security environment with the presence of NATO forces in the country. Suspicions about the presence of NATO troops prevail among Chinese politicians. While Afghanistan expects China to return to an independent policy supported by the country's transparent vision. However, the growing economic interest

⁷O'Neill Aaron. (2022). Total population of the BRICS countries from 2000 to 2027. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/254205/total-population-of-the-bric-countries/> Accessed: September 2022.

and interest in China from the Afghan leadership is indicative of an excellent act of restoring the balance between Kabul and China.

China Foreign Aid Investment in Afghanistan

In 2017, the Belt and Road Forum for International Cooperation took place in Beijing, and a high-level delegation from Kabul is expected to attend in hopes of accelerating many infrastructure projects in Afghanistan. As we mentioned earlier, China became the most important source of foreign direct investment in Afghanistan, especially since the opening of the energy, minerals, and raw materials sector in Afghanistan in 2007. There is also a concern about the crackdown on growing extremism by Uighur jihadists in the Xinjiang region, which borders Afghanistan. The stability of the Belt and Road Initiative requires peace and stability in the Asian and Middle East region. China's economic interest in the region requires China's political and military involvement. In 2016, China signed a Memorandum of Understanding with Afghanistan expressing China's long-term intentions in international relations in the region. Through the OBOR initiative, China is pursuing a geo-economic strategy in the region and solving regional dilemmas. For a better development of energy resources, Beijing is investing in the development of railways and roads, while Afghanistan is the beneficiary of Chinese investments in developing the infrastructure of a country devoid of development during periods of war.

For China's government developing OBOR initiative is crucial. The \$40 billion New Silk Road Fund, \$900 billion of the China Development Bank and a significant share of the \$100 billion Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank are expected to support 900 projects in 60 countries. An offshoot of OBOR, the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor, has also attracted more than \$62 billion in Chinese investment. Any instability emanating from neighboring Afghanistan will limit Beijing's expansive infrastructure and communications ambitions.

OBOR was launched in 2013. China provided about \$240 million in aid to Afghanistan over twelve years between 2001 and 2013. In contrast, in 2015 the company committed to produce \$327 million by early 2017. Beijing also offered 500 scholarships to Afghan students to register in China and train 3,000 Afghans in various professions, including counter-terrorism and agriculture. In addition, China is investing in a \$300 million housing development that could fund 10,000 apartments in Kabul. As a component of the BRI, China is further improving its own connection with Afghanistan. The main train from China was connected to Hairatan in northern Afghanistan via Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. By investing in railroads, China further draws landlocked Afghanistan into an integrated financial system and reduces its dependence on transit routes through Pakistan.

After the withdrawal of American troops from Afghanistan, the issue of security in the region began to be given more attention. Back in 2016, Beijing provided military assistance to Afghanistan. The lack of light weapons, aviation supplies create problems and Afghanistan's interest in logistics. Officially, the presence of Chinese troops near the Afghan borders was refuted, but joint anti-terrorist exercises were repeatedly held.

Sino-Afghan diplomatic relations have noticeably strengthened since 2014. During his presidency, Ghani made an official visit to China in 2014. The countries expanded and strengthened cooperation through conferences (Guts of Asia) and signed a bilateral cooperation agreement in 2017.

Stability in Central Asia can meet China's need to develop economic ties, so China took part in negotiations with the Taliban in 2014 as part of the Quadripartite Coordination Group (QCG). In addition, stability and peace in Afghanistan are the key to the success of economic projects in neighboring Pakistan.

Even by “without providing military forces or significant funding for the reconstruction of Afghanistan”⁸ and withholding any direct military involvement, China has become the country’s most important investor, leading some to accuse it of “freebies” at the expense of others. available data on China's financial contribution to aid and development vary considerably by source. this is evident in a study by Steven A. Zyck⁹ , which attempted to estimate Chinese aid to Afghanistan from 2002 to 2010. He received rather conflicting numbers, ranging from \$58 million to \$200 million.

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) estimated therein period the international contribution for aid and development in Afghanistan of \$33.46 billion. whether or not we consider the highest estimated contribution of China (i.e., \$200 million), it amounted to approximately 0.60% of the entire contributions, which may be a very low figure:

... \$200 million spread across nine years amounts to approximately \$22.2 million p.a. between 2002 and 2010. as compared, research from the Centre for Global Development suggests that Chinese aid globally amounts to between \$1.5 billion and \$2 billion annually. Afghanistan’s share of total Chinese aid is, therefore, relatively minor at roughly 1.10% to 1.47%....¹⁰.

As Zyck noted, Chinese aid to Afghanistan was significant, but aid was given to other developing countries, reinforcing the argument that Afghanistan was not a priority for Beijing, at least until that date. This was important in 2010 despite important agreements reached by both countries in 2006 and early 2010.

A year after Chinese President Xi Jinping announced the BRI, in October 2014, during President Ashraf Ghani's visit to Beijing, China pledged \$327 million to Afghanistan, more than all China's aid to Afghanistan since 2002, which ultimately reflects the modernization of Sino-Afghan relations towards the “strategic partnership and cooperation” agreed in 2012, while “this is a minor amount compared to the \$110 billion in US support for Afghanistan’s economic reconstruction since 2002”¹¹.

While this number is indisputable evidence of Afghanistan's increased role in China's strategic calculus, it does not allow us to extrapolate and establish a relationship with the BRI. Moreover, Afghanistan only signed a formal BRI-related MOU with China (plus some 30 countries) in February 2016. As Ghiasi and Zhou¹² noted, “Some of these MoUs have not yet received much attention, and follow-up actions and commitments from BRI partner countries have not always been visible.” China provided \$10 million in aid to Afghanistan in 2019, excluding disaster relief¹³.

Security maintenance

In this section, we analyze Sino-Afghan security cooperation and evaluate how it relates (or not) to BRI facilitation. We conduct this exercise mainly through the lens of the traditional understanding of security, i.e. associated mainly with

⁸ Zyck A., & Muggah, R.S. (2012). Preventive Diplomacy and Conflict Prevention: Obstacles and Opportunities, Stability. International Journal of Security and Development, 1, 68-75.

⁹ Zyck A., & Muggah, R.S. (2012). Preventive Diplomacy and Conflict Prevention: Obstacles and Opportunities, Stability. International Journal of Security and Development, 1, 68-75.

¹⁰ Zyck Steven. (2012). The Role of China in Afghanistan’s Economic Development & Reconstruction. [online] Available at: https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/Full_Report_3590.pdf. Accessed 18 August 2022: Civil-Military Fusion Centre.

¹¹ Jayaram Nivedita. (2016). Economic Impact of OBOR on Afghanistan. <http://mantraya.org/economic-impact-of-obor-on-afghanistan>. Accessed July 2022.

¹² Ghiasyand Zhou, JiayiRichard. (2017). The Silk Road Economic Belt: Considering Security Implications and EU-China Cooperation Prospects. . SIPRI and Friedrich Ebert Stiftung.: <http://www.sipri.org/publications/2017/other-publications/silk-road-economic-belt>. Accessed JULY 2022.

¹³MENAFN. (2019). Afghanistan-China Pledges 10\$ m in Aid for calamity-Hit Afghans. <https://menafn.com/1098810586/Afghanistan-China-Pledges-10m-in-Aid-for-CalamityHit-Afghans>. Accessed June 2022.

organized instruments of force, primarily military¹⁴, while recognizing, however, other concepts of security that are implicitly dealt with elsewhere in this text.

Insecurity in Afghanistan affects China's security in two important ways: it gives rival powers a reason to keep troops close to their borders, and it makes it easier for Islamic separatist movements operating in China. "While China supports the fight against terrorism and is concerned about the influence of Islamic radicalism in Afghanistan, it also fears the US military presence near its border"¹⁵.

The war on terror against al-Qaeda and later ISIS in Afghanistan and neighboring countries gave us a reason to extend our military presence in Afghanistan and the opportunity to develop military cooperation programs with the countries of Central Asia. Washington's promises that it could withdraw its troops from Afghanistan after the stabilization of the situation in the country without a date were received by China with distrust. "Beijing assessed the growth of the US economy after the 9/11 military presence in Central Asia by receiving and receiving assurances from Washington that its presence is temporary and related to ongoing operations in Afghanistan"¹⁶.

China is incredibly uncomfortable with the American presence in Central Asia.⁴⁷ A large part of "Chinese efforts in Afghanistan are aimed at limiting US influence in the region"¹⁷. Since Afghanistan is the main gateway to Central Asia, China's security interests in Afghanistan are closely linked to China's security interests in Central Asia. In other words, "China has no choice but to view developments in Central Asia as having a potential direct security impact"¹⁸. Despite these misgivings, China was reluctant to demand a military role in Afghanistan and join the counter-terrorism ISAF, but took preventive measures against possible threats to your territory. "Since the American invasion of Afghanistan in October 2001, and even after the fall of the Taliban regime, China has not withdrawn its military forces along the border with Afghanistan or adjacent Tajikistan and Pakistani-controlled Kashmir"¹⁹.

Despite the great activity in Central Asia, the American will to develop close cooperation with the states of Central Asia has suffered some setbacks. The closure of the Manas (Kyrgyzstan) and Khanabad (Uzbekistan) air bases necessary to support US military operations in Afghanistan, and, consequently, the unsuccessful attempt to rent the Ayni Air Force Base (Tajikistan), caused the greatest damage to US aspirations to establish control in Central Asia. This was the result of careful diplomacy between Moscow and Beijing pulling the strings behind the scenes.

Beijing is deeply concerned about the Islamic movements in Central Asia, which have gained worldwide fame and popularity, and the influence they will have on the Chinese Uyghur Muslim community, encouraging its members to take a stronger stand against the central government. Beijing wants to form a belt of stable states around its borders and eliminate the sanctuaries of the Turkestan Islamic Party. China does not want Afghanistan to become a safe haven

¹⁴ Muller Jochen. (2009). The Impact of the Socio-Economic Context on the Länder Parties' Policy Positions. German Politics, Volume 18, 2009-Issue 3.

¹⁵ Swanström & Cornell, S.N., (2001). China Unnerved with War: West so close at its door. . Baltimore Sun.

¹⁶ Lingang. (2005). China's "Good Neighbor" Diplomacy: A Wolf in Sheep's Clothing? Wilson Center. Asia Program Special Report. Asia Report 126.: <http://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/chinas-good-neighbor-diplomacy-wolf-sheeps-clothing>. Accessed August 2022.

¹⁷ Shams Shamil. (2017). What Does China Want to Achieve in Afghanistan? Deutsche Welle: <http://www.dw.com/en/what-does-china-want-to-achieve-in-afghanistan/a-39406187>. Accessed July 2022.

¹⁸ Olcott Marths. (2006). In China a Reliable Stakeholder in Central Asia? Testimony before the U.S.-China Economic and Security Review Commission. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. : <http://carnegieendowment.org/2006/08/04/is-china-reliable-stakeholder-in-central-asia-pub-18606>. Accessed August 2022.

¹⁹ Chung Chien-peng. (2010). China's Multilateral Cooperation in Asia and the Pacific: Institution analyzing Beijing's "Good Neighbour Policy". London: Routledge.

for these groups because it was in the past during the Taliban regime when Uyghurs were trained in camps controlled by Al Qaeda. Beijing wants this not to be repeated in the slightest.

Instability in Afghanistan contributes to the use of Afghan territory by militants to prepare attacks on Chinese territory.

Following the trend in the other two areas, Sino-Afghan security cooperation has expanded in recent years²⁰. Two events contributed to this: the reduction of the NATO presence in Afghanistan, when in December 2014 the ISAF was replaced by the non-combat mission Resolute Support; and the ISIS statement in 2015 that it had absolutely no intention of expanding into the Khorasan region. These developments led to increased cooperation between the two countries, but did not mean that Beijing wanted to replace or take over the role of the US or NATO in Afghanistan.

The Islamic State of Khorasan (IS-K) is a branch of the Central Asian province of the Islamic State that originated in Afghanistan's eastern province of Nangarhar. "Despite initial skepticism about the existence of the group from analysts and leadership, IS-K has been responsible for nearly 100 attacks against civilians in Afghanistan and Pakistan, as well as approximately 250 clashes with US, Afghan and Pakistani security forces since January 2017"²¹. In some provinces, IS-K has become an enemy of the Taliban. "The Chinese government fears that ISIS has gained a foothold in the Afghan province of Badakhshan, on the border with China, and believes the group is persuading a growing number of East Turkestan Islamic Movement (ETIM) supporters to gather there"²².

In response to these developments, China has taken a number of measures. According to some media reports, Beijing has been in talks with the Afghan government to build a military base in Badakhshan Province, near the Sino-Afghan border, within the remote Wakhan Corridor, but both Beijing and Kabul have officially denied this, although according to EurasiaNet.org (2018), some Afghan security officials have confirmed the initial reports. It is assumed that this base will serve to train Afghan soldiers in the fight against terrorism, which will minimize the consequences of reducing the presence of Kabul in certain parts of the territory.

In March 2016, China pledged about \$70 million to support the Afghan government's anti-terrorism initiatives. Four months later, Afghanistan received its first Chinese military aid pledge support from Beijing to help Kabul fight terrorism²³. In addition, Beijing started additional investment in outposts along the Afghanistan-Tajikistan border²⁴. In early 2017, joint Sino-Afghan border patrols began patrolling the Wakhan Corridor to prevent terrorists from entering China. Stanzel Volker regarded these patrols as "evidence of a broader shift in Chinese policy in the region"²⁵. This will not happen, as cooperation in the field of border control has been a standard activity in the region for many years. Afghanistan has signed a military-technical cooperation program with Tajikistan to strengthen the interaction of border forces on the border between Tajikistan and Afghanistan in the fight against terrorism, and Russia has been assisting Tajikistan in border control for several years.

²⁰ ZhangF. (2022). China's New Engagement with Afghanistan after the Withdrawal. . LSE Public Policy Review, 2(3), p.10. <http://doi.org/10.31389/lseprr.52>.

²¹ CSIS. (2018). Islamic State Khorasan (IS-K). <https://www.csis.org/programs/transnational-threats-project/terrorism-backgrounders/islamic-state-khorasan-k>. Accessed June 2022.

²² Stanzel Volker. (2018). New Realities in Foreign Affairs:. Stiftung Wissenschaft und Politik, German Institute for International and Security Affairs.

²³ Gul Ayaz. (2016). China Delivers First Batch of Military Aid to Afghanistan. VOA News [online]: <http://www.voanews.com/east-asia/china-delivers-first-batch-military-aid-afghanistan>. Accessed July 2022.

²⁴ Stratfor. (2016). China Strives to Secure Central Asia. <https://worldview.stratfor.com/article/china-strives-secure-central-asia>. Accessed May 2022.

²⁵ Stanzel Volker. (2018). New Realities in Foreign Affairs:. Stiftung Wissenschaft und Politik, German Institute for International and Security Affairs.

In December 2017, China and Afghanistan agreed to deepen and expand their security cooperation in the fight against terrorism, including border control; and in January 2018, "the Chinese Embassy in Kabul announced that China will provide further military assistance to Afghanistan to help build the capacity of the Afghan army"²⁶.

To counter the destabilizing impact that terrorist organizations can have on regional and national security, in the latter case fueling Uighur separatism in Xinjiang, as mentioned in the first section, China has invested heavily in diplomacy, both bilaterally and multilaterally. Two initiatives deserve special attention: celebrating agreements on the "Good Neighbor Policy" with neighboring countries, which is a priority of China's policy in Central Asia; and the prudent use of the SCO to fight terrorism. China has used the SCO as a forum to encourage the Central Asian republics to isolate the Uighur movement.

With regard to Afghanistan, the Neighborhood Policy has been the subject of numerous interpretations, some more benign than others. Some see it as a tool used by China to expand its economic, financial, security, and diplomatic influence in Afghanistan. Whatever this interpretation, we cannot ignore the element of protection included in the Neighborhood Policy and how this latter has helped China garner support and cooperation from Central Asian states to marginalize Uighur sympathizers and curb their autonomous aspirations and armed opposition to Beijing. China used the SCO as a tool to draw attention to the security of Central Asia and, at the same time, Afghanistan. While contributing to the fight against instability in Central Asia, the SCO has simultaneously contributed to strengthening China's own security, that is, reducing and/or eliminating the influence of rival powers near its borders and, therefore, autonomous aspirations in Xinjiang. The SCO closely coordinates with Afghanistan the fight against the "three forces of evil" (a combination of violent terror, ethnonational separatism and non-secular extremism), as well as anti-drug and economic cooperation. Practical cooperation is carried out within the framework of the Regional Anti-Terrorist Structure (RATS) of the SCO. This cooperation includes, among other things, joint anti-terrorism exercises involving law enforcement and military personnel.

As in the economic sphere, China's security cooperation with Afghanistan has not undergone any significant strategic changes since 2013. The explanations that have prompted China to expand its security cooperation with Afghanistan are not related to the BRI. The agreed cooperation programs did not provide for a specific strengthening of the Afghan capacity to strengthen the protection of the KPEC. Border security cooperation has focused on the northern border, rather than the southern, and specifically on its eastern sections, to prevent the presence of Islamic militant groups and, therefore, the use of Afghan territory to carry out attacks on Chinese territory.

We recognize that a stable Afghanistan has a positive impact on security conditions along the corridors (CCAEC and CPEC) and greatly facilitates transit. But from a security standpoint, China's main concerns are neutralizing Uyghur Muslim separatism, as well as a long-term US military presence in Afghanistan and Central Asia. Beijing is trying at the lowest cost to avoid instability in Afghanistan from spreading and spoiling China's economic plans for the wider region²⁷.

China's key interest in Afghanistan/ Economic interests

Afghanistan has vast deposits of minerals and hydrocarbons, which, according to the Ministry of Mines and Petroleum (MoMP), are valued at an additional \$1 trillion. China's interest in Afghanistan's natural resources has been realized through significant investment, namely two operated by Chinese state-owned enterprises: in May 2008, the China Metallurgical Group Corporation (MCC)/Jiangxi Copper Company Limited (JCL) consortium was awarded a 30-year contract to lease the Mes Ainak copper mine in Logar province for \$3.4 billion, and at the end of December 2011, China National Petroleum Corporation (CNPC) won the rights to drill three oil fields in the Amu Darya Basin in northern

²⁶ Stanzel Volker. (2018). *New Realities in Foreign Affairs*.: Stiftung Wissenschaft und Politik, German Institute for International and Security Affairs.

²⁷ Goh Evelyn. (2016). *Rising China's Influence in Developing Asia*. 67-70: London: Oxford University Press.

Afghanistan (Sari-e-Pul and Faryab provinces) for a period of 25 years for \$400 million.³⁶ If realized these two projects would have made a decisive contribution to the development of the Afghan economy, but this did not happen. Like most Afghan mineral and hydrocarbon deposits, they are located in areas not controlled by the government. and where security can be an issue.

The Mes Aynak copper deposit is considered the second largest in the world and contains about 450 million metric tons of ore and is worth at least \$50 billion. it is a very important asset in order to feed the hungry Chinese industry with raw materials. The MCC offered the Afghan authorities a really generous bonus package. Among other things, it included an additional \$808 million premium and therefore the construction of a transnational railway with two branches, one to the north (Afghan-Uzbek border) and the other to the south (Afghan-Pakistan border), which could cost about 6 billion dollars. Until now, not much has been worn out of Mes Aynak. Rumor has it that MCC wants to renegotiate contracts and has abandoned some of the promised investments related to the operation of the mine. Concerns about a precarious security situation, as well as the discovery of an archaeological site in a mining area, also did not help the project fully provided. established”²⁸.

The three oil fields in the Amu Darya basin are “estimated to contain up to 87 million barrels of oil, which is relatively small compared to larger fields in places like Iran that often contain billions or tens of billions of barrels”²⁹, but the Afghan oil deposits are much larger. As an MCC under the Mes Aynak project, CNPC has also offered generous bonuses to the Afghan government. The plan included the construction of an oil refinery to expand Afghanistan's refinery capacity, which was never realized.

China also tried to induce the concession of the Hajigak Mine, the biggest iron oxide deposit in Afghanistan, located near the Hajigak Pass. But, in November 2011, Kabul awarded four out of the five blocks to a consortium of Indian firms led by the Steel Authority of India Limited (SAIL) and one block to Canada's Kilo Goldmines Patnaik. Still, within the field of natural resources, China is additionally considering the chance of investing within the unexplored Afghan marble industry. China has also been trying to secure a concession for the Khajigak Mine, the largest iron oxide deposit in Afghanistan, located near the Khajigak Pass. But in November 2011, Kabul handed over four of the five blocks to a consortium of Indian firms led by Steel Authority of India Limited (SAIL) and one block to Canada's Kilo Gold Mines Patnaik. Afghan marble industry.

None of China's investments in Afghanistan under the three pillars - aid financing, bilateral trade and natural resources - has a clear reference to the BRI. On the one hand, the most important Chinese investments were planned long before the announcement of the BRI and conceived according to a unique plan and strategy; on the other hand, BRI is “focused on infrastructure development, outsourcing and market creation rather than natural resource extraction”³⁰. China's economic cooperation with Afghanistan has not undergone any significant strategic changes since 2013.

A transnational railway starting at Mes Ainak, which has not yet begun construction, was conceived to support copper mining. it is difficult to imagine it as an infrastructure serving the needs of BRI. Even the Jiangsu-Hairatan railway line, which opened in 2016, which almost completely coincides with the main, easternmost part of CCAWEC,

²⁸ Zyck Steven. (2012). The Role of China in Afghanistan's Economic Development & Reconstruction. [online] Available at: https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/Full_Report_3590.pdf. Accessed 18 August 2022: Civil-Military Fusion Centre.

²⁹ Zyck Steven. (2012). The Role of China in Afghanistan's Economic Development & Reconstruction. [online] Available at: https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/Full_Report_3590.pdf. Accessed 18 August 2022: Civil-Military Fusion Centre.

³⁰ Marty Franz. (2018). Project to Exploit Afghanistan's Giant Copper Deposit Languishes. [online] Available at: <https://www.thethirdpole.net/en/2018/04/16/project-to-exploit-afghanistans-giant-copper-deposit-languishes>. Accessed 20 August 2022.

must be understood because installed capacity maximization and not a project conceived to serve BRI. Afghanistan has a lot to learn in economic terms. BRI's plan, the latter may stimulate and promote its regional integration, but Afghanistan will not be made the center of the BRI project. Afghan dignitaries would indeed like to see Afghanistan become a core element of the BRI, but that wish is hard to come by.

Conclusion

Sino-Afghan relations are built on mutually beneficial combinations of countries. On the one hand, China is interested in the deposits of minerals located on the territory of Afghanistan, and the opportunity to use the country as a short transit route to the countries of the Middle East and choose the stability of the world and the country is gradually changing. China is ready to invest in a country with guaranteed guarantees of invested funds and growth prospects for the Chinese economy. Undoubtedly, the country needs resources that can be processed and are interested in foreign investment. On the other hand, Afghanistan can become a beneficiary of China-Afghan relations. This is the development of the mining industry, and new jobs, and the possibility of economic growth.

China is seeking opportunities to increase the amount of energy mining resources in Afghanistan, which could provide an important link for business and infrastructure development in South Asia and Central Asia, and therefore China's entire share in these regions. China has been contributing to the reconstruction and development of Afghanistan since 2001 through monetary and physical assistance to Afghanistan. The capital of Chinese companies are involved in numerous construction and economic projects of national importance in many parts of Afghanistan, and China has also become the largest foreign investor in Afghanistan, mainly in the mineral and energy sector, which has a very positive impact on the establishment of peace, stability and prosperity in Afghanistan. China needs a stable and peaceful Afghanistan in which it can expand and advance its economic policies. China's approach to Afghanistan is based on four common factors, namely security and stability. economics and governance suitable for Afghanistan, strengthening international cooperation. The essence of Kikai's policy towards Afghanistan is based on the principles of Afghan-led and Afghan-owned initiatives and processes aimed at preserving the independence of the country, its territorial integrity and accepting the path chosen by the people of the country for their progress. Beijing has always advocated the peaceful resolution of conflicts and the maintenance of peace both in Afghanistan and throughout the Middle East region.

The withdrawal of US troops from the territory of Afghanistan opened up new opportunities for Sino-Afghan relations - the Taliban government that came to power was able to maintain peace in the country and is interested in developing international relations with neighboring countries in order to strengthen the power supported by the governments of neighboring countries and develop the country's economy through profitable investments not only from the Chinese side, as the Afghan mineral sector has great potential.

References

1. Adelaja, A., & George, J. (2020). Is Youth Unemployment Related to Domestic Terrorism? Perspectives on Terrorism, 14(5): 41-64.
2. Afridi, H. S., & Afridi, M. K. (2015). NATO Drawdown, Threat Scenarios in Afghanistan and Its Implications for Pakistan and Central Asia. FWU Journal of Social Sciences, 1(1): 1-12.
3. Alizai, M. N. (2015). China can play role in peace, but Afghans must lead process to end. Global Times.
4. Bashardost, Z. (2019). A Comparative Study on the Afghan-China Relation Based on Afghan-US relation. Journal of Social and Political Sciences, 2(2): 285-304.
5. Bhatia, K., & Ghanem, H. (2017). How do education and unemployment affect support for violent extremism?

- Evidence from eight Arab countries. Working Paper 102, Global Economy & Development: 1-40.
https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/global_20170322violent-extremism.pdf
6. Bukhari, S. W. H. (2012). The Role of China ZHU in Economic Stabilization and Reconstruction of Afghanistan. *Margalla Papers*, 16(1): 27-48.
 7. Chung Chien-peng. (2010). *China's Multilateral Cooperation in Asia and the Pacific: Institution analyzing Beijing's "Good Neighbour Policy"*. London: Routledge.
 8. CSIS. (2018). Islamic State Khorasan (IS-K). <https://www.csis.org/programs/transnational-threats-project/terrorism-backgrounders/islamic-state-khorasan-k>. Accessed June 2022.
 9. Daiyar, A. (2009, November 10). China-Afghanistan Trade. *Daily Outlook Afghanistan*.
 10. Ghiasyand Zhou, Jiayi Richard. (2017). *The Silk Road Economic Belt: Considering Security Implications and EU-China Cooperation Prospects*. . SIPRI and Friedrich Ebert Stiftung.: <http://www.sipri.org/publications/2017/other-publications/silk-road-economic-belt>. Accessed JULY 2022.
 11. Goh Evelyn. (2016). *Rising China's Influence in Developing Asia*. 67-70: London: Oxford University Press.
 12. Gul Ayaz. (2016). China Delivers First Batch of Military Aid to Afghanistan. *VOA News* [online]: <http://www.voanews.com/east-asia/china-delivers-first-batch-military-aid-afghanistan>. Accessed July 2022.
 13. Hsiung C. J. (2009). *The Age of Geo-Economics, China's Global Role, and Prospects of Cross-Strait Integration*. *Journal of Chinese Political Science*, 14(2):113-133.
 14. Jayaram Nivedita. (2016). *Economic Impact of OBOR on Afghanistan*. <http://mantraya.org/economic-impact-of-obor-on-afghanistan>. Accessed July 2022.
 15. J. C. (2009). *The Age of Geo-Economics, China's Global Role, and Prospects of Cross-Strait Integration*. *Journal of Chinese Political Science*, 14(2):113-133.
 16. Huasheng, Z. (2012). *China & Afghanistan: China's Interests, Stances and Perspectives*.
 17. Washington D.C.: Center for Strategic & International Studies. https://csis-website-prod.s3.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/legacy_files/files/publication/120322_ZhaoChinaAfghan_web.pdf
 18. Iqbal, H. (2016). *New Trends in Chinese Foreign Policy and the Evolving Sino-Afghan Ties*. *Regional Studies*, 34(2): 1-27.
 19. Izz, V. (2020). *Promoting Decent Employment for African Youth as a Peacebuilding Strategy*. Evidence Synthesis Paper Series. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_emp/documents/publication/wcms744700.pdf Accessed August 2022.
 20. Keita, A. (2015). *Creating good job opportunities at local level: a way to stop young people being attracted to terrorism*. *The Broker: Connecting the World and Knowledge*. <https://www.thebrokeronline.eu/creating-good-job-opportunities-at-local-level-away-to-stop-young-people-being-attracted-to-terrorism/> Accessed August 2022.
 21. Khan, R. M. (2015). *China's Economic and Strategic Interests in Afghanistan*. *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(1): 1-11.
 22. Lingang. (2005). *China's "Good Neighbor" Diplomacy: A Wolf in Sheep's Clothing?* Wilson Center. Asia Program Special Report. Asia Report 126.: <http://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/chinas-good-neighbor-diplomacy-wolf-sheeps-clothing> . Accessed August 2022.
 23. Ludwig, J. Z. (2015). *Sino-Afghan Relations in the Twenty-First Century: From Uncertainty to Engagement*. *Griffith Asia Quarterly*, 3(1): 38-61.

24. Marty Franz. (2018). Project to Exploit Afghanistan's Giant Copper Deposit Languishes. [online] Available at: <https://www.thethirdpole.net/en/2018/04/16/project-to-exploit-afghanistans-giant-copper-deposit-languishes>. Accessed 20 August 2022.
25. MENAFN. (2019). Afghanistan-China Pledges 10\$ m in Aid for calamity-Hit Afghans. <https://menafn.com/1098810586/Afghanistan-China-Pledges-10m-in-Aid-for-CalamityHit-Afghans>. Accessed June 2022.
26. Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Government of Afghanistan, "China-Afghanistan Joint Statement on Deepening Strategic and Cooperative Partnership". <http://mfa.gov.af/en/news/chinaafghanistan-joint-statement-on-deepening-strategic-and-cooperative-partnership>
27. Mudabber Zabihullah. (2016). "Where Does Afghanistan Fit in China's Belt and Road? Cssfom: <http://www.cssforum.com.pk/general/news-articles/foreign-newspaper/109173-where-does-afghanistan-fit-china-s-belt-road.html>. Accessed May 2022.
28. Muller Jochen. (2009). The Impact of the Socio-Economic Context on the Länder Parties' Policy Positions. German Politics, Volume 18,2009-Issue 3.
29. NgT.P. (2010). China's Role in Shaping the future of Afghanistan. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace.
30. Olcott Marths. (2006). In China a Reliable Stakeholder in Central Asia? Testimony before the U.S.-China Economic and Security Review Commission. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. : <http://carnegeendowment.org/2006/08/04/is-china-reliable-stakeholder-in-central-asia-pub-18606>. Accessed August 2022.
31. O'Neill Aaron. (2022). Total population of the BRICS countries from 2000 to 2027. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/254205/total-population-of-the-bric-countries/> Accessed: September 2022.
32. Panda, A. (2014). Afghanistan and China Open a New Chapter. The Diplomat. <http://thediplomat.com/2014/10/afghanistan-and-china-open-a-new-chapter/> .
33. Panda, A. (2015, November 4). Chinese Vice President visits Afghanistan. The Diplomat. Ramachandran, S. (2018). Is China Bringing Peace to Afghanistan? China's role in
34. Afghanistan is undoubtedly growing. What does that mean for the peace process? The Diplomat.
35. Ross, D. G., Trombly, D., & Barr, N. (2014). China's Post-2014 Role in Afghanistan.
36. Washington DC: Foundation for Defense of Democracies.
37. Shams Shamil. (2017). What Does China Want to Achieve in Afghanistan? Deutsche Welle: <http://www.dw.com/en/what-does-china-want-to-achieve-in-afghanistan/a-39406187>. Accessed July 2022.
38. Stanzel Angela. (2016). China's investment in influence : the future of 16+1 cooperation. European Council On foreign Relations.
39. Stanzel Volker. (2018). New Realities in Foreign Affairs: Stiftung Wissenschaft und Politik, German Institute for International and Security Affairs.
40. Stratfor. (2016). China Strives to secure Central Asia. <https://worldview.stratfor.com/article/china-strives-secure-central-asia>. Accessed May 2022.
41. Swanström & Cornell, S.N., (2001). China Unnerved with War: West so close at its door. . Baltimore Sun.
42. Tahiri, N. R. (2017). Afghanistan and China Trade Relationship. MPRA Paper No. 82098, pp. 1-30. <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/82098/>
43. Yongbiao, Z. (2018). China's Afghanistan Policy since 9/11 Stages and Prospects. Asian Survey, 58(2): 281-301.
44. Zia, H. (2019, February 2). A surge in China-Afghan Trade. China Daily.

45. AFP. (2021, August 16). China says ready for friendly relation with Taliban after routing. France 24. <https://www.france24.com/en/live-news/20210816-china-says-ready-for-friendly-relations-with-taliban-after-rout>
46. Aljazeera. (2021, August 26). Kabul bombings: 13 US army personnel killed in attacks at airport. Aljazeera. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/8/26/us-military-personnel-in-bomb-attacks-at-kabul-airport>
47. ABP. (2021, August 30). Afghanistan Crisis: 'All parties should contact Taliban, show them way ahead,' Says China. ABP. <https://news.abplive.com/news/world/afghanistan-crisis-all-parties-should-contact-taliban-show-them-way-ahead-says-china-1479260>
48. ANI. (2021, August 25). China eyes USD 1 trillion of untapped in Afghanistan. ANI. <https://www.aninews.in/news/world/asia/china-eyes-usd-1-trillion-of-untapped-minerals-in-afghanistan-20210825223523>
49. BBC. (2021, September 9). China offers \$31 million in emergency aid to Afghanistan. BBC. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-58496867>
50. BBC. (2021, August 17). Taliban: we will not allow the soil of Afghanistan to be used against anyone. BBC. <https://www.bbc.com/news/av/world-asia-58249178>
51. Brown, S. (2021, July 8). Withdrawing from Afghanistan makes sense, but Biden's execution is a disaster. USA Today. <https://www.usatoday.com/story/opinion/2021/07/08/chaotic-afghanistan-withdrawal-dismisses-our-sacrifices-disabled-vet/7890546002/>
52. CGTN. (2021, September 17). China calls for solidarity among SCO members as the bloc turns 20. CGTN. <https://news.cgtn.com/news/2021-09-17/Xi-Jinping-addresses-SCO-meeting-via-video-link-13D3zqRd34k/index.html>
53. CGTN. (2021, July 28). China urges Afghan Taliban to fight against ETIM terrorists. CGTN. <https://news.cgtn.com/news/2021-07-28/Wang-Yi-meets-with-Afghan-Taliban-delegation-in-Tianjin-12grE7drmlW/index.html>
54. CGTN. (2021, August 14). Chinese diplomat: U.S. bears 'inescapable responsibility' for Afghanistan's situation. CGTN. <https://news.cgtn.com/news/2021-08-14/U-S-bears-inescapable-responsibility-for-Afghanistan-s-situation-12IphvoB6Mg/index.html>
55. Digital, E. (2021, August 21). 'Saudi Arabia of Lithium' -Afghanistan's gold, oil, copper estimated well above \$3 trillion. ET Now Digital. <https://www.timesnownews.com/business-economy/economy/article/saudi-arabia-of-lithium-afghanistan-s-gold-oil-copper-estimated-well-above-3-trillion/801992>
56. FP. (2021, August 19). SCO set to come into focus as China, Russia, Iran inch towards recognizing Taliban regime in Afghanistan. First Post. <https://www.firstpost.com/india/sco-set-to-come-into-focus-as-china-russia-iran-inch-towards-recognising-taliban-regime-in-afghanistan9896661.html>
57. Gardner, F. (2021, August 27). Afghan airport attack: Who are IS-K?
58. BBC. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-58333533>
59. Gersen, W. (2021, September 28). Column: A Marshall Plan for Afghanistan. Valley News. <https://www.vnews.com/column-gersen-afghanmarshalplan-082921-42154772>
60. Haider, S. (2021, July 5). China has a big plan for Post US Afghanistan, and it's worth billions. Daily Beast. <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/859668-china-has-a-big-plan-for-post-us-afghanistan-and-it-s-worth-billions>
61. Hass, R. (2021, August 18). How China will seek to profit from the Taliban takeover in Afghanistan. Brookings. <https://www.brookings.edu/blog/order-from-chaos/2021/08/18/how-will-china-seek-to-profit-from-the-talibans-takeover-in-afghanistan/>

62. Husain, F. (2021, August 21). Game Changer. Dawn. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1641755>
63. Hussain, T. (2021, September 3). Enemies after 9/11, US and Taliban inch towards uneasy alliance against ISIS-K. SCMP. <https://www.scmp.com/week-asia/politics/article/3147356/enemies-after-9/11-us-and-taliban-inch-towards-uneasy-alliance>
64. Horowitz, J. (2021, August 19). The Taliban are sitting on \$1 trillion worth of minerals the world desperately needs. CNN. <https://edition.cnn.com/2021/08/18/business/afghanistan-lithium-rare-earths-mining/index.html>
65. Hashimi, H. (2021, September 9). China extends \$31m in emergency aid to Afghanistan. Aljazeera. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/9/9/china-offers-31m-in-aid-3-million-covid-shots-to-afghanistan>
66. Jiamei, W. (2021, September 7). Afghan reconstruction not a zero-sum game for China, Pakistan. Global Times. <https://www.globaltimes.cn/page/202109/1233617.shtml>
67. Jin, W. (2021, September 4). The unbridgeable divisions between the Afghan Taliban and ISIS-K. CGTN. <https://news.cgtn.com/news/2021-09-04/The-unbridgeable-divisions-between-the-Afghan-Taliban-and-ISIS-K-13hhvFA873a/index.html>
68. Jun, X., & Daye, C. (2021, July 13). Extension of CPEC into Afghanistan to boost local exports, journey of peace: analyst. Global Times. <https://www.globaltimes.cn/page/202107/1228518.shtml>
69. Jones, S. & Blanchette, J. (2021, September 13). China's Afghanistan dilemma. Foreign Affairs. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/china/2021-09-13/chinas-afghanistan-dilemma>
70. Kou, M. (2021, August 2). China in Afghanistan: Trade and Terrorism.
71. The Diplomat. <https://thediplomat.com/2021/08/china-in-afghanistan-trade-and-terrorism/>
72. Li, S. (2021, August 16). China's conflict mediation in Afghanistan. Stimson. <https://www.stimson.org/2021/chinas-conflict-mediation-in-afghanistan/>
73. McDonnell, T. (2021, August 16). The Taliban now controls one of the world's biggest lithium deposits. Quartz. <https://finance.yahoo.com/news/taliban-now-controls-one-world-154420425.html>
74. Marsden, M. (2021, September 15). China, Afghanistan, and the Belt and Road Initiative: Diplomacy and Reality. The Diplomat. <https://thediplomat.com/2021/09/china-afghanistan-and-the-belt-and-road-initiative-diplomacy-and-reality/>
75. Miller, C. (2021, August 25). Pakistan support to Taliban: What to Know. Council on Foreign relations. <https://www.cfr.org/article/pakistans-support-taliban-what-know>
76. Mohanty, K. (2021, September 7). Why Taliban see China as an extraordinary opportunity as they look to rebuild Afghanistan. News 18. <https://www.news18.com/news/explainers/explained-as-they-look-to-rebuild-af-why-taliban-see-china-as-an-extraordinary-opportunity-4175267.html>
77. Mohsin, S. (2021, August 18). U.S. Freezes Nearly \$9.5 Billion Afghanistan Central Bank Assets. Bloomberg. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2021-08-17/u-s-freezes-nearly-9-5-billion-afghanistan-central-bank-assets>
78. Musavi, S. M. A. (2021, August 31). Afghan Analysts Sharply Criticize US's Hasty Withdrawal. TOLO News. <https://tolonews.com/afghanistan-174458>
79. PTI. (2021, September 13). China ask US, world to provide aid to Afghanistan to avert crisis post-Taliban takeover. The Print. <https://www.newindianexpress.com/world/2021/sep/13/china-asks-us-world-to-step-up-aid-to-afghanistan-to-avert-crisis-post-taliban-takeover-2358205.html>
80. Putz, C. (2021, September 14). More than \$1.2 billion in humanitarian aid pledge to Afghanistan. The Diplomat. <https://thediplomat.com/2021/09/more-than-1-2-billion-in-humanitarian-aid-pledged-to-afghanistan/>
81. Peter, M., & Oladele, O., & Green, B. (2020, February 20). Education in and for the Belt and Road Initiative: The pedagogy of collective writing. Taylor & Francis Online. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2020.1718828>

82. Patonia, A. (2021, September 10). Lithium and an unexpected battle for energy transition in Afghanistan. *The Diplomat*. <https://thediplomat.com/2021/09/lithium-and-an-unexpected-battle-for-energy-transition-in-afghanistan/>
83. Sakhi, N. (2021, June 18). How Russia, China, and Iran will shape Afghanistan's Future. Atlantic Council. <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/new-atlanticist/how-russia-china-and-iran-will-shape-afghanistans-future/>
84. Sayed, A. (2021, August 29). ISIS-K is ready to fight the Taliban. Here's how the Group became a major threat in Afghanistan. *The Washington Post*. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/opinions/2021/08/29/abdul-sayed-isis-k-taliban-afghanistan-threat> Accessed 18 August 2022
85. Sweeney, P. (2021, August 16). Afghanistan put China firmly on leadership hook. Reuters. <https://www.reuters.com/breakingviews/afghanistan-puts-china-firmly-leadership-hook-2021-08-16/>
86. Tanvir, M. H. (2021, September 4). Taliban Leadership vs ISKP in Afghanistan: A Cause of Concern. *Paradigm Shift*. <https://www.paradigmshift.com.pk/taliban-leadership-vs-iskp-in-afghanistan/> Accessed 18 August 2022
87. Times, G. (2020, September 22). US and allies bear main responsibility for Afghanistan's reconstruction: Chinese, Russian and Pakistani envoys. *Global Times*. <https://www.globaltimes.cn/page/202109/1234840.shtml>
88. Xinhua. (2021, September 9). Chinese FM attends first meeting of FMs from Afghanistan neighbors. *Xinhua net*. http://www.news.cn/english/2021-09/09/c_1310176148.htm Accessed 18 August 2022
89. Xinhua. (2021, September 23). Chinese FM urges lifting economic sanctions on Afghanistan at G20 meeting. *China Daily*. <http://global.chinadaily.com.cn/a/202109/23/WS614c3b74a310cdd39bc6b0ab.html> , Accessed 18 August 2022
90. Xinhua. (2021, September 14). China to donate COVID-19 vaccines to Afghanistan: diplomat. *Xinhua*. http://www.china.org.cn/world/2021-09/14/content_77751175.htm Accessed 18 August 2022
91. ZhangF. (2022). China's New Engagement with Afghanistan after the Withdrawal. *LSE Public Policy Review*, 2(3), p.10. <http://doi.org/10.31389/lseppr.52>. Accessed 18 August 2022
92. ZiaH. (2019). A surge in China-Afghanistan Trade. *China Daily*.
93. ZyckA., & Muggah, R.S. (2012). Preventive Diplomacy and Conflict Prevention: Obstacles and Opportunities, Stability. *International Journal of Security and Development*, 1, 68-75.
94. ZyckSteven. (2012). The Role of China in Afghanistan's Economic Development & Reconstruction. [online] Available at: https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/Full_Report_3590.pdf. Accessed 18 August 2022: Civil-Military Fusion Centre.

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